

BLENDING DESIGNS FOR COMPOSITE PLATES WITH TWO CONCENTRIC LAY-UPS UNDER COMPRESSION

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SUMMARY

It has been demonstrated in literature using plates with two concentric lay-ups under compression lighter configurations can be formed than is the case for single lay-up geometries. Present work elaborates on this by optimising the stacking sequence of both concentric lay-ups whilst enforcing continuity between them, also referred to as blending. Optimisation and blending are achieved by means of a multi-chromosomal genetic algorithm, separating the blending procedure from fitness evaluation.

The results show substantial weight improvements can be achieved over the best known constant stiffness design. Furthermore, the blending operation seems to have no negative impact on structural performance.

Keywords: Composite, Laminates, Buckling, Optimisation, Laminate Blending

1 INTRODUCTION

As in all thin-walled structures buckling plays a dominant role in the design of composite plates and shells. Various authors have studied the behaviour of composite plates under compressive and shear loads [9, 11, 15]. Recent work by Kassapoglou [4] and Papadopoulos and Kassapoglou [10] studied the behaviour of plates with two concentric lay-ups under compression and shear. To this end a Raleigh-Ritz based approach to model such plates was developed.

The obtained results show significant improvements in buckling performance of composite plates can be achieved by subdividing panels in two or more rectangular regions of different lay-up and thickness, keeping panel weight equal to a specified single lay-up baseline geometry. This leads to believe concentric lay-up designs can also be used for weight minimisation with a buckling load constraint. In this work the aforementioned Raleigh-Ritz-based approach will be adopted to study weight minimisation of a simply-supported rectangular plate with two concentric lay-ups under compression.

One of the biggest issues in designing a composite structure of more than two lay-up regions is the continuity of one stacking sequence into the other. In order to achieve a structurally coherent design, the panel should be designed such that for adjacent lay-ups at least a predetermined minimum number of plies continue from one lay-up into the other. This activity generally is referred to as blending.

Since its introduction by Kristinsdottir *et al.* [5], several forms of blending fibre composite laminate structures have been considered. Continuity constraints to enforce stacking sequence continuity [6] showed that up to a certain point substantial increase in continuity can be obtained for only a small weight penalty. Another approach employing design variable zones and sub-laminates found a much smaller weight penalty [14]. Using a distributed GA within a parallel processing environment with migration [2] fully blended solutions were obtained, however, at high computational expense. The excessive computational cost were addressed by simplifying the blending problem [1] introducing a guiding stack from which all laminates in a structure are obtained by deleting a contiguous series of outermost or innermost plies. Designs obtained by this method are intrinsically blended, a reason for which it has been used in further blending research [3, 13]. However, this definition of inner and outer blending [13] restricts the optimisation problem to a small region of the design space. Exploiting the fact GA operations themselves are quite modest in computational cost Van Campen *et al.* [16] investigated the use of more general blending definition. For these generalised definitions blending is no longer an intrinsic part of the design process, making the optimisation more demanding on the part of the GA.

Present work focuses on the weight optimisation of a simply-supported rectangular plate with two concentric lay-ups under compression and the impact of laminate blending there on. The problem at hand serves as a realistic example for laminate blending of structures with strong structural interaction between design regions; the assumption is that next to stacking sequence design material redistribution in this type of structure plays a key-role in the buckling performance. A total of four blending strategies will be compared to one another. Optimisation will be carried out by a multi-chromosomal GA, based on the encoding scheme of McMahon *et al.* [7, 8].

In the following, first of all laminate blending and its implementation in a GA frame work will be discussed, after which the formulation of the optimisation problem will be treated. Finally the results obtained for a square plate of 20 by 20 inch and two different sizes for the centre patch will be discussed.

2 LAMINATE BLENDING

Design of the laminate stacking sequences for multi-region composite structures with ply continuity across region boundaries is generally referred to as blending [13]. Blending aims primarily to aid manufacturability of the structure and reduce possible stress concentrations at panel boundaries [1]. Here we define the blending problem as the stacking sequence optimisation on multiple interconnected regions with a global performance constraint. Goal of the optimisation is determination of the stacking sequence of each region resulting in a minimum weight structure satisfying the enforced blending definition.

Using a guide-based genetic algorithm (GA) to perform structural optimisation there are two classes of blending that can be considered. The first class to be mentioned here decodes the genetic information, with which the GA works, inherently into blended designs. The second class requires a more active roll on the part of the GA, i.e. individuals are decoded in a straightforward fashion and blending is taken care of by genetic operators. Before looking at these two classes, first of all the multi-chromosomal encoding scheme to be used will be discussed.

2.1 Multi-Chromosomal Encoding

In the present study the blending operation is handed over to the GA. Therefore, a parametrisation based on a multi-chromosomal GA representation is proposed. This way it becomes possible to separate the stacking sequence design from the guide and the selection of plies from the guide per region. To this purpose the encoding scheme of McMahon *et al.* [7, 8] has been modified.

Many similarities exist between the individual's structure proposed and the parametrisation traditionally used for guide-based blending [1, 3, 12, 13]. The main difference is the fact that an individual now contains multiple chromosomes, instead of only one, though Seresta *et al.* [13] also used multiple chromosomes per individual, but in a more restrictive fashion.

Two types of chromosome are distinguished, *guide chromosomes* (defined by McMahon *et al.* [7, 8] as laminate chromosomes), and *region chromosomes*. The guide chromosome encodes the guiding stack for the overall structure using integer valued orientation genes. The integer value of each orientation gene will correspond to an orientation alphabet defined by the user. To give an example, the integer values $V_0 = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ can be defined to translate to the following set of orientations: $\{0^\circ, \pm 15^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, \pm 75^\circ, 90^\circ\}$. In the same fashion a material gene and alphabet can be added, linking material data to a coded integer value. Each individual contains one guide chromosome, and additionally one region chromosome per lay-up region of the structure. The region chromosome (referred to as panel chromosome in previous work [16]), is an addition to the original framework of McMahon *et al.*, and consist of a binary sequence equal of the same length as the guide chromosome. Each region in the structure is designated its own region chromosome, defining which layers from the guide are used to construct the laminate for the region in question. The binary genes work as switches. If a switching gene takes on the value 1, the corresponding orientation and material gene are used for the construction of the encoded region. For a zero value the corresponding layer of the guide is not used. After reading the entire chromosome this way the lay-up for the given region has been determined.

To give an example let's consider the following individual.

guide chromosome:	3	7	5	1	7	2	3	2
region chromosome:	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1

In combination with the orientation alphabet discussed before this individual encodes the laminate $[\pm 30 / \pm 60 / 0 / 90 / \pm 15]_s$ when considering symmetric laminates constructed from fabric material.

2.2 Interpretation Enforced Blending

A ply can only be considered blended from one region to another if for both regions the switching gene in the region chromosome has value 1, i.e. the ply will occur in both regions and can thus continue from one region to the other. In the above the interpretation of individuals encoded by the multi-chromosomal encoding scheme used in this work, based on the encoding scheme of McMahon *et al.* [7, 8], has been discussed. This interpretation allows for unblended individuals to be represented. One option to deal with this would be to modify the interpretation of the individual in such a way that only blended are representable. The definition of inner and outer

blending [13] would be very suitable for this approach.

By definition for inner (or outward) blending per region a contiguous set of outer plies is dropped from the guiding stack, leaving the remaining plies, closest to the mid-plane of the laminate, to continue from one region to another. Outer (or inward) blending is just the opposite of inner blending, deleting a set of contiguous plies from the guide starting from the laminate’s mid-plane. Figure 1 shows inner and outer blending in a schematic form, for four adjacent regions. Region I in the figure may be considered to have all the layers in the guide. Regions II and III have one and two layers, respectively, dropped from the guide. Note that in this approach what is designed is the guide and the number of layers dropped from this guide in each region.

Figure 1: Inward and outward blending.

By adding up the values of the switching gene, it is possible to determine the number of plies to be taken from the guide per region. Taking these plies as a contiguous set from either the mid-plane or the outer surface of the guide, inner and outer blending are established respectively as shown in the following example:

guide chromosome:	3	7	5	1	7		inner blending
region chromosome 1:	1	0	0	1	1	→	region 1: $[\pm 60/0/90]_s$
region chromosome 2:	0	1	1	0	0	→	region 2: $[0/90]_s$
							outer blending
						↙	region 1: $[\pm 30/90/\pm 60]_s$
						↘	region 2: $[\pm 30/90]_s$

Blending can thus be enforced by the interpretation of the individual leading to inherent blending of the structure to be designed. However, there is no room for the possibility of skipping a few layers and then dropping layers, reducing the design space. A main advantage is the easier genetic search that is possible, though a weight penalty might result due to the inflexibility to specify a more general ply-drop schedule.

2.3 Genetic Operator Enforced Blending

As mentioned previously, unblended designs can be represented by the multi-chromosomal encoding scheme used in this work. Rather than rigid blending enforcement in individual interpretation the blending task can also be handed over to genetic optimisation. This would require incorporation of a blending term in the fitness function of the GA. In previous work [16] this approach has been studied for two blending strategies taking advantage of the more general setting offered by the multi-chromosomal representation, dealing with blending in a more generic sense.

The first definition, illustrated in figure 2(a) is as follows:

Generalised blending definition: *We consider two adjacent panels completely blended if all the layers from the thinner panel continue in the thicker one regardless of their position along the thickness of the laminate.*

To express this definition in a mathematical form severable variables will be introduced here. S_A and S_B are considered as the boolean strings for adjacent regions A and B, respectively. Only when both regions have corresponding 1's a layer will be continuous. Thus the set of continuous layers C can be defined as the intersection of S_A and S_B , $C = S_A \cap S_B$. The total number of plies m occurring in the thinner panel without occurring in the thicker one can then be calculated, shown in equation 1.

$$m = \min \left(\sum S_A, \sum S_B \right) - \sum C \quad (1)$$

Where m is defined as the number of mismatched layers between two regions. According to the generalised definition a panel is considered only blended if $m = 0$.

A panel is only blended according to the generalised definition if $m = 0$. Any positive integer will therefore indicate that not all the layers of the thinner laminate continue into the other panel, yielding the candidate design unblended.

(a) General blending, all layers of the thinner region continue in the thicker region. (b) Relaxed generalised blending, no dropped plies are in physical contact.

Figure 2: Example of generalised and relaxed generalised blending.

The generalized blending definition can be further relaxed to the following form, illustrated in figure 2(b):

Relaxed generalised blending definition: *“We consider two adjacent panels completely blended if there are no dropped edges in physical contact.”*

For the relaxed generalised blending definition no edges should be in physical contact. Edges that are in physical contact with one another will be referred to as *butted edges*. Assuming there are c continuous layers ($c = \sum C$), along with vector I_c containing their indices in the pair of

region chromosomes under consideration, we define $j = I_c^i + 1$ and $k = I_c^{i+1} - 1$, where i is the index of the continuous layer in C . Then j and k can be used to define the sets of discontinued layers in both regions A and B, given in equation 2.

$$\begin{aligned} j \leq k &\rightarrow nc_A^i = \sum_{n=j}^k S_A^n, & nc_B^i &= \sum_{n=j}^k S_B^n \\ j > k &\rightarrow nc_A^i = nc_B^i = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where nc_A^i and nc_B^i are the number of dropped layers between continuous layer i and layer $i+1$ of panels A and B, respectively. The number of butted edges b can be determined from this number, as shown in equation 3.

$$b = \sum_{i=1}^c \min(nc_A^i, nc_B^i) \quad (3)$$

The relaxed generalised blending definition is only satisfied if $b = 0$, i.e. there are no butted edges.

The obtained number of mismatched plies or butted edges, depending on the blending definition, can be used to penalise the fitness function of any individual for which they don't equal zero. Results obtained in doing so are not fully satisfactory [16]. One cause for which might be the reduced selective pressure on other performance criteria. A bigger problem however is possible generation of unblended offspring by blended parents, as will be demonstrated here for the crossover operation on two region chromosomes, the vertical line indication the crossover location.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} & & & & & \text{Blended parents} \\ & & & & & \times \\ \begin{array}{cc|ccccc} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{array} & & \begin{array}{cc|ccccc} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} & & \begin{array}{cc|ccccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{array} \\ & & \downarrow & & & \\ & & \text{Unblended children} & & & \\ \begin{array}{cc|ccccc} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{array} & & \& & \begin{array}{cc|ccccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \end{array}$$

Thus a considerable amount of the produced offspring will not satisfy the blending definition, even when their possibly highly fit parents do, hampering the genetic search.

Also there is the computational expense involved. The framework used, allows to test on *blendedness* of the design without the need to evaluate the fitness function for the individual at hand. In most cases the GA operations will be computationally less expensive than the fitness function evaluation. It would make sense to only evaluate the fitness function of those individuals that fulfill the blending definition. Therefore, in this work unblended individuals are discarded and genetic operations are repeated until a blended individual has been obtained to replace the unblended individual in the population.

3 OPTIMISATION FORMULATION

As demonstration of the improved implementation of the generalised and relaxed generalised blending definitions weight minimisation of a square panel with two concentric lay-up regions

under compressive loading, as shown in figure 3, will be considered. In this specific example plain weave fabric will be used with properties: $E_{11} = E_{22} = 67.5\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = 4.48\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{12} = 0.05$. Plate dimensions are 20×20 inch and two size of centre patch size are considered, 10×10 and 18×18 inch respectively.

Figure 3: Panel with two concentric lay-up regions.

The optimisation problem is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f(x) \quad x \in X \\ \text{such that} \quad & g_j(x) \geq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, n_g \end{aligned}$$

where f is the normalised weight of the panel as function of design variables, and n_g is the number of inequality constraints g_j imposed on the problem. For the weight optimisation at hand the only imposed constraint is the panel's buckling load to be equal or larger the buckling load of the base-line design. For implementation of this problem by a GA the objective and constraint functions must be combined into one fitness value. An effective way of doing this is to make use of an augmented fitness function. To this end the constraints have to be normalised in such a way that a constraint value of -0.1 corresponds to 10% constraint violation, and a value of 0.1 corresponds to 10% margin. The most critical constraint $g_{\min} = \min g_j$ defines the design margin. Negative design margins correspond to an infeasible design and thus can be used to penalise the fitness function by multiplying the negative design margin with penalty parameter β , and subtracting the resulting value from the the fitness value of the individual (because βg_{\min} is negative this will lead to an overall increase of the fitness function value). A small bonus parameter ε can be used to discriminate between feasible designs of equal weight, by multiplying it with the design margin and subtracting this from the fitness function. The augmented fitness function as described takes the following form:

$$\Theta = \begin{cases} f - \beta g_{\min} & \text{if } g_{\min} < 0 \\ f - \varepsilon g_{\min} & \text{if } g_{\min} \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

As mentioned the used objective function is panel weight. Because the density of the material used remains unchanged also panel volume can be used for this function. The resulting objective function is given in equation 5, in which the dimensions correspond to those in figure 3.

Table 1: Optimisation results for 10×10 inch centre patch

Blending type	Lay-up		Weight reduction	λ
unblended	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)]_s$	0.00%	1.0055
	Centre	$[(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_8]_s$		
inner blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_6/(0/90)_2]_s$	0.00%	1.0000
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)_6/(0/90)_2]_s$		
outer blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)/(\pm 45)_2/(0/90)]_s$	0.00%	1.0000
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)/(\pm 45)_2/(0/90)]_s$		
general blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_2]_s$	0.00%	1.0000
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_2]_s$		
relaxed generalised blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_6/(0/90)_2]_s$	0.00%	1.0000
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)_6/(0/90)_2]_s$		

$$f = \frac{(AB - ab)t_{\text{perimeter}} + (ab)t_{\text{centre}}}{V_{\text{baseline}}} \quad (5)$$

The buckling load of the panel is compute using analysis proposed by Kassapoglou [4]. From this the constraint margin is computed, equation 6.

$$g = \lambda - 1 \quad (6)$$

Where λ is the buckling load factor. Furthermore the values $\beta = 5$ and $\varepsilon = 0.01$ are used.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As baseline design the best known 16 ply lay-up in terms of uni-axial buckling load is chosen, $[(\pm 45)_8]_s$. Goal is to find any lighter designs that can withstand the same buckling load. To this end weight optimisation has been performed for two centre patch sizes, 10×10 and 18×18 inch. The results of the optimisation are given in tables 1 and 2.

For all cases the genetic algorithm was set to use 50 individuals per iteration, and to terminate if after more than 50 iterations no improvements were found, with a maximum of 500 allowed iterations. Only two ply orientations are considered (0/90) and (± 45) .

It is seen, that for the 10×10 inch centre patch, no weight improvement is possible, and all designs, except the unblended one, come up with constant stiffness designs. A possible explanation might be found when looking at the relation between centre patch dimension and buckling load keeping the weight of the panel constant. In the graph shown in figure 4 the centre patch dimension has been varied for a constant D-matrix ($[(\pm 45)_n]_s$ for an infinite number of layers), and several ratios of perimeter and centre patch thickness. Buckling load improvements are only found for patch size dimensions close to the panel's dimension, especially so for the case of a thinner centre lay-up (blue curves). For the 10×10 inch case a centre patch thickness

Table 2: Optimisation results for 18×18 inch centre patch

Blending type	Lay-up	Weight reduction	λ
unblended	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_5/(0/90)/(\pm 45)_2/(0/90)_4/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_3]_s$	1.9631
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)/(0/90)_3]_s$	
inner blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)/(0/90)_6/(\pm 45)_8/(0/90)_2]_s$	1.7757
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)_2/(0/90)_2]_s$	
outer blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_3/(0/90)_2/(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)_3/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_3/(\pm 45)/(0/90)]_s$	1.7801
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)_4]_s$	
general blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_3/(0/90)_2/(\pm 45)_4/(0/90)_3/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_3/(\pm 45)/(0/90)]_s$	1.1013
	Centre	$[(\pm 45)/(0/90)_2]_s$	
relaxed generalised blending	Perimeter	$[(\pm 45)_3/(0/90)_6/(\pm 45)_3/(0/90)/(\pm 45)_3/(0/90)_3]_s$	1.0452
	Centre	$[(0/90)/(\pm 45)_2]_s$	

other than that of the perimeter is thus very likely to result in a buckling load reduction, or a weight penalty.

Figure 4: The effect on buckling load of centre patch dimension variation

For the 18×18 inch case weight reductions of up to 26.88% are found. In all cases material from the centre of the panel was moved to the perimeter, as was already suggest by examination of figure 4. More interestingly, the generalised and relaxed generalised blending definitions indeed seem to produce lighter blended designs than inner and outer blending. For inner blending even a slight weight increase is observed. It is noted that for these designs the buckling load factor λ is also considerably larger than one. Better convergence of the generalised blending definitions might be contributed to the larger number of genetic operations they require, but this is subject to further investigation.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper it has been shown it is possible to incorporate more generalised blending definitions successfully in a genetic algorithm (GA), based on a multi-chromosomal framework. The blending operation is separated from the fitness evaluation, letting only blended individuals survive. The blending operation itself is found to have no negative impact on structural performance. However, in future research more fibre angle directions should be taken into account, also studying the use of uni-direction material.

Performing weight optimisation on panels with concentric lay-up regions using a GA with the aforementioned multi-chromosomal framework substantial weight reduction appears achievable compared to the best known constant stiffness design. Weight reduction up to 26.88% is reported, however it is noted this is only for the case of uni-axial compressive loading. In future research more load cases should be included.

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